

VOCABULARY FEATURES OF SPECIALIZED SPORT PUBLICATIONS

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The lexicographical principles of sports terms, the thesaurus method in creating a dictionary, the characterization of words related to the field as terms in the Uzbek language in the translation of sports texts have been thoroughly analyzed in cross-sectional aspect.

In linguistics, there are such stable and stable word combinations that create the expressiveness and imagery of speech, and their appearance is due to people's views on objects and events in objective existence, strongly connected with relations. Members of society use linguistic means based on various comparisons in order to express their views and attitudes towards things and events in an exciting, figurative and impressive way. In this sense, the depicted person, thing, event and phenomenon, the scene of the world is often interpreted through images or similes well known to the listener. To describe the lexical-semantic features of the terminological system in depth, we should use the thesaurus method (thesaurus-dictionary method).

The main difference between a thesaurus (ideological, ideographic, conceptual dictionary) and an explanatory dictionary is that in explanatory dictionaries the words are arranged in alphabetical order and the meaning of the word is given in the form of a definition, while in the ideographic dictionary-thesaurus there are semantic, meaningful categories, which are based on certain criteria and are based on classifications, and as a result, words represent this meaningful category.

One word can be included in several semantic categories of the thesaurus, because it can have several general meanings, and in one of the general meanings of the

word, it can be integrally connected with several conceptual areas. For example: Court is included in the word class associated with jurisprudence / advancement of justice, on the other hand, Court is included in the word class associated with the concept of sports.

For example: Court - 2. Magistrate, bar, session. Types of courts include the following – the supreme of the United States, appellate court of the United States, Federal court, district court, country court, justices court, magistrate's court.

Tarjimasi: (adolatni qaror toptirish uchun vosita) sud, skameyka, magistratura, bar, sessiya. Sudlarning turlariga quyidagilar kiradi: Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlari Oliy sudi, Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlari apellyasiya sudi, Federal sud, shtatlar oliy sudi, okrug sudi, tuman sudi, adliya sudi, magistratura sudi, mer sudi, polisiya sudi.

Court - 4. (an area for playing certain games) arena, rink, ring, diamond, track, course, racecourse, golf course, race tracks, stadium¹

Tarjimasi: (ma'lum bir o'yinlarni o'ynash uchun maydon) maydon, rink, ring, olmos, trek, yugurish, golf maydoni, poyga maydonchalari, stadion.

From the above definitions, it can be concluded that it is correct to describe each word using a certain set of classes included in the thesaurus.

Between the thesauri of the world and the scientific field, there is not a specific language, but the structure of knowledge in the scientific field (a unique view of the worldview reflected in the ²totality of specially selected or specially created situations)². In this regard, we have analyzed the lexical unit club related to the field of sports. included in the gear (tool) group; in texts on the subject of

¹ Webster's New World Thesaurus / Ed. By Charlton Laird. - New York: New American Library, 1975. - 678p.

² Webster's New World Thesaurus / Ed. By Charlton Laird. - New York: New American Library, 1975. - 678p.

weapons, the lexeme club means club (weapon).

It is included in the constituent/component group, entertainment, social, in the description of texts - the night club is included in the groups related to the specific concept of space (space) in the general sense and leisure center (recreation center) in the specific sense.

Sports lexicon means a wealth of vocabulary that reflects activities that require both physical and mental energy and strength from a person, embodying professional and recreational activities in a person.

On the other hand, by general sports lexicon, we should understand a specific lexical layer based on non-scientific concepts, expressed in language, related to "speakers of the middle social class", reflecting the concept of sports, belonging to the linguistic landscape of the world.

Thus, it is no exaggeration to think that the main word defining the conceptual relationship in SLT is the lexical unit "Sport / sport". Associative relations with this main unit, it is appropriate to divide all sports lexical units into 14 thematic groups (TG):

1. Kamondan otish va o‘q uzish – Archery and Shooting
2. Velosport va motosport – Cycle Racing and Motorsports
3. Ot sporti – Equestrian Sports
4. Qilichbozlik – Fencing
5. Baliq ovlash sporti – Fishing Sport
6. O‘yinlar – Games (Olympic games)

7. Havoda suzish va havo sporti – Gliding and Aerial Sport
8. Gimnastika – Gymnastics
9. Ov qilish sporti – Hunting Sport
10. Alpinizm – Mountaineering
11. Engil atletika bo‘yicha tadbirlar / atletika – Track and Field Events / Athletics
12. Suv sporti – Water Sports
13. Og‘ir atletika va jangovar sport turlari – Weightlifting and Combat Sports
14. Qishki sport turlari – Winter Sports.

All things considered it can be concluded that no fragment (part) of a certain whole (wholeness) independently constitutes a whole (wholeness), unlike representatives of a certain genus belonging to the corresponding species. These linguistic relations represent the terminal nodes and the existing constituents in the thematic groups that make them up. Hence learning sports terminology in the terms of conveying approachable ideas from sports to viewers plays a key role in the terms of not only enjoyment of spectators, but also crystal-clear translation of the sports event.